

Citizens' perceptions on trust and data management: do we need to create data commons?

Abstract

Most of the existing regulatory framework on personal data, such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), is structured around individuals and their control over data. However, emerging technologies, particularly those based in data sharing intensive practices, pose a challenge to individuals given the power asymmetry between them and the platforms that operate such activities. As a response, certain regulatory initiatives have emerged to introduce new data governance schemes, such as the Data Governance Act (DGA), in the form of data cooperatives, intermediation services, or data altruism organizations. Such mechanisms evolve with the goal of returning power to data subjects by granting them democratic control over their personal data and choose to pool their rights over their data. To do this, data co-operatives play the role of trustees and manage data on behalf of data subjects. Therefore, data subjects retain democratic control over their data once they respond to the question of who they should trust with their data. Given this background, we have followed a citizens' science methodology around the notions of self-control over personal data, through decentralised personal data stores, or pods, and sharing such control within the family context to explore these ideas in practice.

Keywords: PIMS, trust, personal data, governance, GDPR, DGA

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1. Introduction

Many countries are pushing a policy agenda that seeks to develop the data economy, i.e., an economic model based around the intensive exploitation of information to foster growth. Part of the involved information includes personal data related to individuals. At the same time, a considerable and growing number of jurisdictions have enacted rules that seek to govern how this kind of information can be used, putting in place requirements to ensure the respect for fundamental rights. The main premise of this data economy is to put in circulation as much data as possible so that it can be processed using Big Data techniques, particularly by enabling the sharing and re-use of personal data. For example, the EU Data Strategy is an example of these policy strategies, which is already producing regulation to enable this in domains like health or scientific research, where individuals' consent is expected to play a key role.

However, the further use of data comes with its challenges. Most of these regulations are based around two ideas: (i) a capable individual to make reasonable and informed decisions about every single bit of its personal data; and (ii) an individual-centric perspective that only considers the person alone and without considering its social connections. When it comes to the first issue, and as researched in different fields, individuals are overwhelmed by digital choices and it is possible to expect that these interactions would only grow in the future under these data economy policy strategies. As for the second issue, there has been research that personal data about individuals can have implications beyond themselves and affect others, which would call for a different data governance scheme that contemplates a group/common perspective over data.

In response to these challenges, both legal and technical answers have emerged. Regarding the first, new data governance schemes, such as data sharing pools, data co-operatives, or public data trusts, constitute an alternative while keeping up with the existing approach around the individual. On the other hand, personal data sovereignty alternatives enabled through technological means seek to facilitate how choices are made (Wang & De Filippi, 2020). With these tools, it is expected to improve trust on

centralized services in order to enable the envisaged data economy. However, there is limited research in the field around how these tools, both regulatory and technical, would actually achieve their objectives. Therefore, we decided to take a citizens' science approach and focus on a field that will soon see regulation that approaches these issues. In this sense, we have arrived at the following research question: 'What are the citizens' perceptions on novel data governance schemes to manage their health and family data?'

This contribution is structured as follows. Section 2 will present the technical background that motivated the research that led to this study. Section 3 will present the study conducted under a citizens science approach and its findings. Section 4 shall explore the notion of trust and how it can configure the decision-making process around privacy. Section 5 picks up this from a regulatory perspective to explore whether regulation can improve trust. Finally, Section 6 will explore whether current ethical and regulatory frameworks can provide a group-based approach to personal data.

2. The emergence of decentralized data governance systems: the case of SOLID

Computer scientists and developers have put forward several implementations to address the overwhelming number of choices that individuals need to make daily; through these, data subjects can reclaim their data in a more effective manner using, for example, personal information management systems, usually known as PIMS (Janssen et al., 2020). In this context, the use of decentralized PIMS may be the answer for users to regain control over who has access to their data and under what conditions.

However, centralized services, such as Facebook, LinkedIn, or Twitter, currently control the flow of data on the Web. These technological companies collect large amounts of personal data in their data silos, making it difficult for the users to have access to their data, let alone to reuse it in other Web services. While some regulation, such as the Digital Markets Act in the European Union, is expected to address this by empowering users to block certain practices undertaken by these service providers while at the same time facilitating the porting of data from one service to another, expanding the existing

right to personal data portability. Nevertheless, its effects will only be seen years in the future once it becomes enforceable, much like what happened with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). In addition, the terms and conditions of these services are sometimes presented to users in a manner that is not transparent regarding their data handling practices and in ways that do not allow users to specify their privacy preferences. Regulation has also tried to improve this, but results have been, to say the least, mixed regarding the effectiveness of such an approach.

The common pattern across this is the predominant reliance on individuals' consent to approve or negate certain data processing activity. As mentioned above, this has caught the attention of technical experts and much effort has been dedicated towards solutions that would facilitate this. Despite this, their success has been questionable and for some time efforts were stopped or diminished.

On the other hand, in the last few years, we have been following the development of this new wave of technologies that are based on the concept of decentralization. Examples of these systems are the blockchain-powered technologies, which are, for instance, decentralising financial transactions, i.e., Bitcoin, and the Semantic Web stack of technologies which are decentralising access to the data on the Web. In practice, decentralised systems detach the data from the service itself, providing the users with full control over the data because of it being kept in personal data stores. With the data stored in this type of PIMS, users can regain control over what information the services have access to and reuse the same data across different applications.

One example of these technologies is Solid, a project led by the inventor of the Web Tim Berners-Lee, is a specification for decentralised personal online data stores ("Pods") based on interoperable Web standards and protocols. Solid allows its users to take ownership of their data by storing and managing the access to it, while Solid applications have access to this information through dynamic access control rules that the users themselves choose. Moreover, Solid applications and Pods are interoperable since the data generated by any Solid app can be stored in any Pod, independently of the Pod provider. In addition, Solid applications are also interoperable since the data generated

by one application can be reused by another. A list of approved Pod providers is maintained by Solid for the users to choose according to their terms and conditions and there is also the possibility to self-host their own Pod.

Moreover, Solid implements authentication and authorisation protocols as two processes to improve users' trust in the privacy and security of their data. When it comes to the authentication protocol, Solid uses the WebID specification which allows for each agent to have a unique identifier. Therefore, the WebID is used to authenticate the users when logging in to Solid applications and for the users to manage the data on their Pods. Additionally, the access rights on a Pod are attached to specific WebIDs regardless of the user to which they relate.

On the other hand, the authorisation protocol in Solid is based on the Web Access Control (WAC) specification. Using WAC, each resource in a Pod can have a set of authorisation statements that are stored in the so-called Access Control List Resources (ACLs). These statements include the authorised agents and the modes of access that they have to the resources. Additionally, these authorisations can be explicitly set for an individual resource, inherited from the parent folder, or even set at the pod level, which can be easily set by the users, for instance using a drag-and-drop option, so that they do not have to understand what is happening behind the scenes with the ACLs code.

A decentralised system such as Solid brings in a few advantages. First, by default, access to the resources is not allowed unless the user gives active consent, which is aligned with the GDPR principle of privacy by default and by design. Another strong aspect is related to the fact that permissions can be set to local files or at a broader level, for instance over folders or even over the whole Pod, and it is much easier to update and revoke access than on the usual centralised applications. On the other hand, some disadvantages still need to be overcome, such as creating a mechanism to specify prohibitions, i.e., if a user wants to state that he does not want his / her data to be used for the development of commercial products. Also, in line with the previous point, there is still work on the way to be able to write authorisations over specific types of data or specific purposes.

3. Studying citizens' perspectives on SOLID-based schemes

While PIMS have existed for quite some time, the possibilities enabled by SOLID and the myriad of developments around the Semantic Web have not been explored with end users. Moreover, considering the key role that data subjects would play in this new scenario, it was agreed that the public at large should be consulted. However, the lack of clear information demanded the adoption of an exploratory approach to test whether citizens are interested in questioning current data usage practices and asking whom they should trust with their information. This triggered our initial research questions and defined our intended exploratory study.

a. Citizen Think-In overview

In this respect, it was selected the format of a "citizens' think-in". These types of events are public forums in which people come together to discuss some of the ethical and legal issues we face in the digital age. It facilitates two-way community dialogue to create awareness among citizens and researchers about responsible technology development and use. A Citizens' Think-In differs from the more traditional panel discussion or public lecture event as it encourages direct participation from the attendees. Through small group discussions, a Think-In provides an opportunity for people from diverse walks of life to deliberate and discuss topical societal issues arising from Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) innovation.

In particular, the format of the Think-In was selected because it allows "to provide a public Think-In in which to hold conversations on controversial or unresolved societal issues related to science and technology" (Grehan et al., 2020) In this respect, the matter of trust in digital services and new digital intermediaries is, indeed, unresolved.

Each Think-In comprises: an introductory presentation on key concepts, that in this case was about personal data sovereignty and trust in online activities; small-group discussion of several technology application scenarios focusing on opportunities,

impacts, risks, and benefits of the main topics; and report-out by each group on its thoughts and recommendations, followed by whole-group discussion. Such Citizens' Think-Ins address calls in European policy discourse for two-way dialogue between sciences and the public which empowers them as scientific citizens. More specifically, they aim to enhance participants' understanding of the main topic and its potential impact on their lives and society; strengthen citizens' and scientists' familiarity with, and acceptance of, diverse points of view related to the main topics; and grow participants' confidence in participating in public discourse about STEM and their feelings of being engaged with STEM research.

The Think-Ins consisted of the following sections: welcome and set out the aims of the session; an introductory presentation on the question "Who Should I Trust With My Data?"; two breakout rooms for small-group discussion of two co-created scenarios, detailed below; report-out by each group on its thoughts and recommendations; and whole-group discussion.

The main question used to guide the discussion, 'Who should I trust with my data?', was drafted by the involved researchers after analysing the proposed regulatory framework and the technologies involved. In that moment, the proposed Data Governance Act was put forward by the European Commission to generate trust in data subject around the idea of sharing their personal data under the envisaged data economy model. New data governance schemes, particularly data cooperatives, contemplates the possibility of assisting the data subject in making online choices rather than relying exclusively on the disclosure information provided by the data controller, particularly those that can be considered as BigTech. As such, the question around trust emerged in our preparatory work and guided our efforts. By questioning this idea, it was possible to explore how citizens perceived these novel models and the results, as it will explore in section 5, showed that certain existing social structures might tackle this.

The results presented here are a result from our exploratory study, conducted in June 2021. From the 46 attendees registered, 14 attended the Think-In event (30% attendance; 70% drop off). This was a lower turnout than the previous Think-In run by

ADAPT on 4 March (47% attendance; 53% drop off). Potential reasons for a lower turnout include fewer COVID-19 restrictions - in March 2021, Ireland was in Level 5 lockdown and most people were working from home and restricted to a 5km travel limit, but by 9 June, the restrictions were lighter with retail and hospitality open; and improved weather that allowed outdoor activities.

To conduct the think-in, we relied on the following roles:

Host: introduced the Think-In format, the involved institutions, and the ground rules and expectations for the event. Also managed the Zoom breakout rooms and guided the general flow of the event.

MC: introduced the expert speaker; gave instructions for the small group discussions in the breakout rooms and facilitated the report-out and discussion sections of the event.

Speaker: gave a general overview of new legislation under the, then proposed, draft Data Governance Act.

Facilitators: three Think-In facilitators were placed in breakout rooms to help encourage the flow of conversation and the contribution of each participant in their small-group discussion. Facilitators provided a summary of the guidelines for the discussion and introduced one of two discussion scenarios to their group.

Scribes: Two Think-In scribes acted as note-takers and rapporteurs during the small group discussions. Their notes were used to report back to the whole group at the end of the Think-In. The notes are archived as they may provide valuable information which may help inform future research and relevant public policy in the discussion area.

b. Citizen Think-In procedure

The speaker introduced the topic of new legislation under the, then proposed, Data Governance Act. This has led to the proposed introduction of new data governance models and trusted intermediaries to improve trust between individuals who share their data with BigTech organisations. Shared personal data spaces, or Data pods such as those based on Solid, were presented as a potential solution for decentralised data storage. Participants were asked to consider a series of scenarios relating to their data.

Through carefully crafted scenarios, participants were introduced to concepts around digital privacy in their own home, the networks they use, ways to manage their data, and how it interfaces with larger applications and websites at the event. The scenarios were developed through a co-creation workshop with participants from different organizations. We will expand this in the following subsection. Participants were asked to consider questions about :

- A. Are there any circumstances where you would be willing to make decisions about sharing your family's data? What circumstances would these be?
- B. Do you feel confident to make an informed decision about sharing sensitive family personal data with third parties? What would make you feel more confident?
- C. Who do you trust to help you understand requests to share data and why would you trust them?
- D. If the company looking after your data (e.g., pod provider or trusted data steward) wanted help designing the online form to read which would be used to approve personal data requests from third parties, would you be willing to help them?

c. Webinar and co-creation workshop

To raise awareness about our intended citizens consultation, we conducted a webinar on 7 May 2021 to discuss some of the issues that motivated our research in this topic. After that, eight people participated in a co-creation workshop held on Zoom on 20 May 2021 to explore the question: **"Who Should I Trust with My Data?"** During the workshop, small group discussions were used to draw from citizens' expertise and experience to identify themes related to the question. We recruited these participants in many ways from advertising on social media channels to internal and external newsletters. We also circulated it to local public networks.

The Padlet tool was used to record notes taken in two discussion groups. The themes identified in the workshop were subsequently considered for inclusion in the scenarios that were used at the Citizen's Think-In on 9 June 2021. Once the scenarios were finalised, a follow-up meeting was offered to the co-creation participants to discuss the scenarios and to ensure that their contributions, where included, were accurately represented. However, there was no take-up on an in-person session when offered though one person expressed feedback via email which was noted and responded to.

d. Think-In Scenarios

As a result of the discussions in the co-creation workshop, two scenarios were developed, and are outlined below:

Scenario 1: Sarah's Android Watch

Information about ourselves and our families is constantly collected through our phones and devices. Data about our location, preferences, interests, and, even more, sensitive information such as our health or wealth is collected and stored by apps and other services. However, the purpose of this data collection is not always clear, when it comes to this data being shared. New EU legislation has been proposed to provide a legal framework that can then be used to identify such trusted data stewards.

Mary decides to get her daughter Sarah an Android smartwatch. The watch has health tracking and data-sharing features. These are an added benefit, given that Sarah suffers from epilepsy. Mary can now keep track of both Sarah's health indicators as well as her location in case she has a seizure while out somewhere. The information is collected by the smartwatch and transmitted to Mary's Android phone thanks to Google Cloud's services. Mary starts to receive marketing emails from insurance companies offering their neurological service coverage. She wants to find out who the data collected by the watch is shared with and for what purposes.

Scenario 2: Jane's Data Pod

Our health information is often spread across different locations like our GPs, in hospitals, private clinics and now even on our phones as the use of smart wearable devices that track and collect our fitness data increases. A decentralised space that can store these different types of data could improve people’s access and control over their own data. “Data Pods”, such as in Solid, are personal online data storage spaces. These are a new way for people to store their own data on their own Pod and not online resulting in more control over who they want to share it with. Jane’s GP informs her that they have a new data pod system for managing patient health data. Jane does some research and agrees to have her personal data stored in a shared family Pod, along with her daughters’ data.

e. Findings

As noted above, the Citizens’ Think-In was the culmination of a process that consisted of a preparatory webinar for a co-creation workshop. In each stage, it was possible, to a higher or lesser degree, the interaction between the researchers and the public. In this sense, feedback about the topic in question was collected at different moments. In Table 1, we summarize the main findings and, if there was repetition between the stages, it is also acknowledged.

Table 1 Summary of the main findings during the think-in process

“Idea” / Concern / Priority	Webinar	Co-creation	Think-in
Enforcement of law	X		
Remedies to address failures in trust	X		
Regain power in data trusts (models)	X	X	
Educate citizens in privacy and data protection	X		
Relation between trust and explainability	X		

"Idea" / Concern / Priority	Webinar	Co-creation	Think-in
Different social classes and different attitudes towards controlling data	X	X	
Being indifferent to data control due to lack of awareness of the negative consequences of losing control over one's data	X	X	
Challenges of EU – non-EU personal data transfers due to technological developments	X		X
Will more regulation address this?	X	X	
Data subjects trust public entities more than private entities	X	X	X
Government entities should foster trust		X	X
The type of data conditions and the desired level of control over it		X	X
Current form of terms & conditions/privacy notices is meaningless, and language is too complex		X	X
Collaboration between public and private sectors towards fostering trust		X	

"Idea" / Concern / Priority	Webinar	Co-creation	Think-in
Avoid turning protecting regulation, such as the GDPR, into a checkbox compliance exercise		X	X
Public bodies should have control over and oversight data flows		X	X
Individual (enforceable) control over data through technological developments (personal data stores) could play a great part	X	X	X
Balance time spent on data managing and convenience of not worrying about it		X	X
Relevance of "personal" (in particular, family) relations to foster trust in online services		X	X
Concern about sensitive data types such as health or financial data		X	X
Possibility to share personal data only for certain purposes or to third parties		X	X
Relevance of consent as an enabler of data sharing			X
The reputation of big vs small companies			X
Create a standard for privacy rating of companies			X
Return on investment of providing personal data			X

"Idea" / Concern / Priority	Webinar	Co-creation	Think-in
The reverse of education (from children to parents) about data literacy			X
Govern the data of vulnerable data subjects (elderly, mental illness, children, ...)			X
Existence of guiding/recommending, bodies that can point out to more "trustworthy" entities			X
Tailored information for the specific moment where it is needed			X
Use of dynamic consent and technological developments for it			X
Involvement of users in the process of creating the privacy notice			X
Different degrees of trust in social relationships and institution-based relationships			X
Sharing data only for the people who are not able to make decisions			X
International bodies to go beyond the limits of GDPR			X

This table was drafted by all the involved researchers by observing the notes taken down during the different stages. To avoid or mitigate any potential bias in the highlighting of

topics given the background of each researcher given the different backgrounds, this task was conducted at the same time by all involved researchers.

While all three events introduced different issues, due to having different participants in each of them, it is possible to identify common patterns among the three stages leading up to, and including, the Citizens' Think-In. In this regard, the common topics are the following:

- individual (enforceable) control over data through technological developments (personal data stores) could play an important role; and
- data subjects trust public entities more than private ones;

The main shared topics show that individuals are, to say the least, curious about the idea of potential greater control and oversight over their data by themselves or by public authorities. As it was described in section 2 of this paper, in the last few years, there has been a rise of technical solutions to allow data subjects further control over their data. The exact details of how these solutions operate differ between each of them. From all these solutions, one of them is, Solid, as it relies on Web standards and protocols which are in line with the ideas of interoperability and portability promoted by the legislation in this domain.

While it was identified that citizens might have more trust in public bodies rather than private companies, the regulation proposals mentioned above (the DGA and the eIDAS amendment) contemplate the participation of both types of entities in the new data governance schemes. In this respect, it is necessary to wait for concrete developments and implementations to further analyse if these initial perceptions correspond with better or worse data practices.

In connection with these central topics, discussed in the co-creation process and the Citizens' Think-In, it was possible to identify shared themes:

- The balance time spent on data management against the convenience of not worrying about it.
- Relevance of “personal” (in particular, family) relations to foster trust in online services.
- Concern about sensitive data types such as health or financial data.
- Possibility to share personal data only for certain purposes or to third parties.
- Government entities should foster trust.
- The type of data conditions and the desired level of control over it is important
- Current form of terms & conditions/privacy notices is meaningless, and the language is too complex.
- Collaboration between the public and private sectors is needed towards fostering trust.
- Avoid turning protecting regulation, such as the GDPR, into a checkbox compliance exercise.
- Public bodies should have control over and oversight of data flows.

In this respect, the reaction to the scenarios proposed for discussion as part of the Citizens' Think-In was positive since the participants in this event shared the views that were used as inspiration for their drafting. Therefore, while the samples were small in numbers for quantitative analysis, a qualitative approach and interpretation of these results show that regular individuals from a variety of backgrounds share the same concerns and are interested in the same solutions. On the other hand, the feedback from the citizens engaged in the Think-In confirmed the relevance of the topics proposed to the citizens in the co-creation process and the trends identified by the researchers for the initial webinar.

Particularly, citizens have raised the issue of avoiding turning the GDPR into a ‘tick-box’ compliance exercise that has produced the current form of privacy notices, which would be the case of deploying a template privacy notice for several different data processing activities. Moreover, disclosure and oversight over the use of personal data in a practical and useful manner would be a key topic that demands attention. In this sense, meaningful transparency to build trust between the stakeholders is, consequently, a relevant issue.

A particularly interesting issue that emerge during the co-creation workshop and the Think-in is that on the relevance of certain social relationships to secure trust in online services. However, on the other hand, this did not imply that a commons-like structure could emerge to consolidate and represent individuals, in this case family members. The individuality that serves as basis for regulation, as it will be addressed in the following section, would seem to be engrained in the participants' perception around to whom the data belongs and who should make choices around it. In this sense, parents making choices for their children would seem from existing legal frameworks around minors' decision making rather than from the existence of a shared data pool.

The discussions held during both the co-creation workshop and the citizens' think-in could lead us to the following reasoning. Novel data governance models fostered by regulation such as the DGA are intended to address the question of trust around centralized service provider that have a history of failing end users. A technical response to this has been through the decentralization phenomena and the re-emerge of PIMS. However, certain data subjects might not be fully able to make these choices anyways. As such, social interactions by group members, such as those made by a parent on behalf of their, could provide a solution. In this sense, when someone trusts others (even groups) to do X for them, they trust them to make decisions on their behalf or even put them in anonymous groups. However, this does not necessarily constitute the creation of a data commons among these individuals, even more so if the legal regime around personal data does not allow for this. In the following sections, we will pick these findings before existing literature.

4. Trusting relationships between intimates and among strangers

The two cases mentioned in section 3 were prepared with the intention of crediting the hypothesis developed by Waldman that “spheres of privacy mirror spheres of trust: when we trust, we share; when we do not trust, we do not share ... Our sense of when our privacy is invaded is similar to the sense of our trust being breached” (Waldman, 2015, p. 564). Regarding this, Case 1 is an example of a privacy invasion due to the

breach of the trusting relationships between Sarah, whose right to privacy is waived to her mother, and a stranger who collects and even has access to her data. In contrast, Case 2, Jane's Data Pod, does not represent a privacy invasion due to the trust-based relationships among family members. The main idea of this section is to discuss trusting relationships among individuals, as in case 2, and between individuals and organisations or agents who collect and have access to information, as in case 1. To accomplish this, we should first define trust and then describe trustworthy relationships between intimates and strangers.

The kind of trust implicated when we share things with or interact with others is three-place trust: *A* trusts *B* to do *x*, where *x* can be keeping shared information confidential. This kind of trust is sometimes considered to be entirely based on past knowledge (Waldman, 2015). Hardin argues that "for me to trust you, I have to know a fair amount about you" (Hardin, 2000, p. 34). Parsons states that trust between persons required common values and common goals: "people defined as sharing one's values or concrete goals in whose competence and integrity one has 'confidence' come to be thought of as 'trustworthy individuals' or 'types'" (Parsons, 1978, p. 47).

Trust can develop among intimates, family members and friends. Trust may emerge over time as the result of an iterative interaction among intimates (Blau, 2017); this type of trust is relatively simple to comprehend and generally considered reasonable. In Case 2, for example, members of a family trust to each other to keep shared information confidential. Accordingly, trustworthy relationships with others creates a context in which members of a family, or a data pod, associate privately with one another, sharing feelings and emotions, making plans and acting in accordance to achieve their goals. A trust-based context protects the interests of each individual member in association privately with one another. Given that "family or relational privacy" refers to the protection of members' interests in respect to others and ensuring the integrity of associates with others (Bloustein, 2019, p. 124), developing trust-based relationships in a disclosure context protects relational privacy.

Even without the opportunity of a repeated game, trust among strangers can be just as robust and long-lasting as trust between intimates. Recalling Case 1: Sarah's Android Watch. How can Sarah's mother and the stranger who collects (or had access) to Sarah's data build trusting relationships? Trust among strangers emerges when the person or institution in charge of collecting data fulfils some obligations to ensure data subjects that the context is trustworthy and, thus, a reasonable place to share personal data. Obligations of the recipients of personal information include discretion, honesty, protection, and loyalty.

Firstly, the most fundamental assumption made by people when revealing personal information is that the recipient will be discreet. Discretion, defined as "the quality of behaving or speaking in such a way as to avoid causing offense or revealing private information" is an implicit part of most information relationships. Trust is preserved when trustees exercise sound discretion in choosing what to whom personal information is revealed to them. Secondly, trust in information relationships requires an affirmative obligation of honesty and be open with those who disclose personal information to them. Thirdly, in order to preserve a trust, trustees must protect data against attackers, secure databases, and act affirmatively in the interest of data subjects (or data holders). This is the obligation of protection. Finally, loyalty entails avoiding self-dealing at the expense of the trustee (Richards & Hartzog, 2015, pp. 459–471).

So far, we have discussed trusting relationships among intimacies, such as case 2, and among strangers, such as case 1. Regarding sharing information in a data pod, the question may arise is how to ensure that privacy is protected when those sharing information in, for example, a data pod are not family members. Followingly the question is how to build relationships based on trust so that people can share their data in such environments and enable them to negotiate their privacy with each other within a data pod. In section 2, we looked at whether technology advancement can deal with these issues. Furthermore, it is important to consider how far data protection law encompasses the essential obligations required to establish trusting relationships between data subjects and recipients of personal information, such as organisations or other agents. In section 5, we will examine how data protection laws accommodate for

groups, if so at all, to secure trust among these strangers, while questioning the ethical grounding of such an approach .

5. Can we accommodate group perspective into existing ethical and legal frameworks?

To explore this section of our contribution, we first need to mention that privacy and personal data protection are two distinct rights (González Fuster, 2014). For the purposes of this contribution, we are focusing on the latter, however, we acknowledge that certain threats to privacy also have an impact on personal data protection. The focus of personal data protection on the individual in Europe, can be traced back to Convention 108 which created a link between data protection and the right to privacy as enshrined by Article 8 of the European Convention on Human Rights (Gonzalez Fuster, 2014, p.89). Convention 108 provided principles for subsequent European legislation, including Directive 95/46 on Personal Data, and the General Data Protection Regulation and as a result this legislation has remained focused on the individual.

a. Are groups introduced in new EU data-related regulation?

All these regulations have been based around the idea of putting in place rules to cover up for any lack of trust between data subject and data controller; however, individuals are losing their ground as their main point of reference. Group privacy and group data protection perspectives have gained attention as they could provide answers due to privacy and data protection threats posed by emerging technology are more likely to affect groups rather than mere individuals, something not originally conceived by the personal data protection rules. Big data, for example, is more likely to treat types (of customers) than tokens (you), and thus groups rather than individuals (Floridi, 2014, 2017). This makes us think about the possibility of dealing with these threats using data protection rights but on a group level.

It is frequently assumed that ascribing rights to a group as such entails ascribing moral status to the group as such, corporate approach to group rights. If groups can be right-

holders in the same way that individuals can, it may appear that a right-holding group must have moral standing equal to that of an individual right-holder (French, 1984). We only ascribe rights to beings to whom we ascribe standing, so assigning rights to groups as such may appear to imply assigning standing to groups as such. Giving moral standing to groups, on the other hand, is something that liberals are generally opposed to (Jones, 2010).

However, this does not imply that we should abandon group accounts and return to individualist accounts of rights to privacy and data protection. We must take the concept of group rights to privacy and data protection seriously, but in a consistent way with our current anthropocentric ethical framework. While the so-called first and second waves of human rights are associated with liberal and welfare (either social, economic or cultural) political perspectives, respectively, the third wave is pegged to solidarity between human beings. In this context, rather than assigning rights to a mysterious supra-individual entity that is beyond and apart from those of individuals, groups and collectives of individuals are granted (joint or collective) rights directly on behalf of *all* members of such array of people, collective approach to group rights (Jones, 1999; Raz, 1988).

Due to the shortcomings in the existing liberal approach to personal data governance, policymakers and regulators, particularly within the context of the European Union, have responded with, what seems to be, 'innovative' data governance schemes to propose alternatives so as to amend the present failures. In this respect, it is possible to identify the emergence of four clear paths: (i) data sharing pools; (ii) data co-operatives; (iii) public data trusts; and (iv) personal data sovereignty (Craglia et al., 2021).

But where do we find these new alternatives in the regulatory framework? If we analysed the current legislative and regulatory developments, we could identify two main instruments that are pushing forward the agenda on these topics: (i) the Data Governance Act (DGA); and (ii) the 2nd electronic IDentification, Authentication and trust Services Regulation (eIDAS 2). There is still another instrument in the regulatory pipeline of the European Commission, the Data Act, whose text still needs to be made public. Of

these two proposed new legal instruments, one of them has amassed a particularly large collection of criticism: the DGA. In this respect, both academia (Baloup et al., 2021) and authoritative bodies (European Data Protection Board and European Data Protection Supervisor [EDPB-EDPS], 2021) have adopted a critical take on the proposal and the intended new data governance structures to be created.

How does the DGA exactly deal with groups and group-based rights? For this, we must look at the provisions dealing the data cooperatives but also data altruism. Data cooperatives are envisioned as entities that will facilitate collaborative pooling of data by individuals or organisation for their benefit (Baloup et al., 2021). While this is a step towards the recognition of the group in data governance in the EU, the DGA does not ascribe a distinct legal standing to data cooperatives (Baloup et al., 2021); as a matter of fact, Recital 31 of the DGA states as follows: ‘In this context it is important to acknowledge that the rights under Regulation (EU) 2016/679 can only be exercised by each individual and cannot be conferred or delegated to a data cooperative.’ Furthermore, the DGA does not provide for rights to the group in the same manner as the GDPR.

Given that all these new alternatives should be applied and interpreted alongside the GDPR, the individual, i.e., the data subject, remains at the very core and groups remain something only those individual decisions can form. There might some margin for the introduction of a group-based right to data protection through the data altruism organizations, but the DGA proposal remains silent on this point, merely addressing the incorporation of personal data by individuals relying on their consent. As such, the EU Commission has doubled down on the liberal approach to personal data protection and, particularly, the use of technologies that allow for such an approach, such as personal information management systems or, even, decentralized data spaces, such as SOLID. Therefore, the DGA, just like the GDPR, would only be interested in fostering trust between individuals rather than between groups and centralized data controllers.

b. What can the GDPR do for groups?

As we have been discussing in the previous sections, the GDPR constitutes, so far, one of the cornerstones of personal data governance regulation that has had a global influence (Bradford, 2020). Despite its approach when it comes to developing data commons or group-based approaches, it is worthy to dedicate some words to the introduction of the accountability principle and the risk-based approach to data protection made by the GDPR (Gellert, 2018). The notion of risk management is not strange to the realm of regulations, such as in the case of financial services regulation or environmental law. Its basic premise can be summarized as follows: '[t]he aim of assessing risk is the estimation of negative impacts through consistent processes, thus the mitigation, avoidance or other acceptable forms of treatment will become achievable' (Böröcz, 2016, p. 473).

However, the risk to whom should be mitigated, avoided or treated? In this sense, Böröcz (2016) argues that risk can be related to (i) the individual, (ii) the group, (iii) society, and (iv) others. Considering this, we can question which path was taken by the GDPR and its regulatory offspring across the world. While most authors argue that the GDPR has adopted an individualistic perspective on risk management, it is also true that the wording used contemplates to some degree the existence of a group, albeit not granting them rights directly. This is prominent in provisions that require data protection impact assessments (DPIA) to be conducted in the GDPR. The GDPR requires controllers to seek the views of data subjects or their representatives when conducting a DPIA where processing is likely to result in high risk to rights and freedoms of natural persons. This requirement provides an opportunity for the enhancement of group data protection rights (Ritsema van Eck, 2019).

This is because groups whose rights and freedoms could be impacted by the proposed processing can make representations of the risks posed by the proposing to their rights and freedoms. However, this requirement suffers from a major flaw when it comes to ensuring that group rights to data protection are factored in legislation. The inclusion of data subjects or their representatives is voluntary, and their views will only be sought where a controller deems it appropriate.

The GDPR also provides a mechanism in Article 80 for Member states to create legislation that allows representative actions against individuals or entities that are responsible for an infringement of personal data protection laws. While this does not specifically offer a group right to data protection, it provides a route for collective action in the face of infringements of the GDPR. The Court of Justice of the EU (CJEU) in the case of *Meta Ireland Limited v Bundesverband der Verbraucherzentralen und Verbraucherverbände* held that consumer protection groups can bring collective or representative claims without authorisation from the affected consumers for violations of the GDPR. The CJEU found that Article 80 did not exclude or override national laws that allow consumer groups to bring actions for violations of the GDPR without the mandate of the affected data subject. Thus, when a group thinks that there has been a violation of the GDPR they may file a suit without the authority of the affected data subject.

This could be used by groups to assert their rights against infringements of the GDPR where the violations have an impact on members of their group without the group having to find a member to mandate litigation. However, there is a caveat in the judgement by the CJEU, collective litigation without a mandate is permissible where the option is provided for by Member State law. In the absence of member state law, a consumer group would have to have the mandate of the affected data subject.

This is as far as current legislation provides for groups rights in relation to data protection. The GDPR is an awkward fit for group rights to data protection due to its focus on individuals (Ritsema van Eck, 2016, p.298). European law on data protection treats personal data as a final linkage between an individual and a larger group (Puri, 2021). This excludes any notion of a group right to data protection though there is a trend towards realisation of a group dynamic in upcoming legislative proposals at the EU level such as those discussed above.

c. Going back to ethics to improve protection?

While there is ground to build a group-based approach to data governance, our legal and technical backgrounds limit this approach. However, this does not mean that rights cannot be assigned to a group. Instead, by respond to the following questions, we can continue to defend *moral* group rights: (i) who is the holder of a moral group right?; (ii) why should moral group rights be respected?

To determine who the holder of a moral group right is, it is important to analyse different views of the holder of a group right. As mentioned previously, the corporate and collective approaches are the two most discussed views of a group right holder. According to the corporate approach, what distinguishes a group as the type of thing that might hold right is that the group possesses an identity that is not changed whereas some or all of the persons included in the group change (French, 1984; Newman, 2004). However, according to the collective approach, there must be public goods that can only be held by collectively, not individual. In respect of the publicity of production of such goods, or the joint activity nature of such goods in Miller's (2001) view, and the publicity requirement for its enjoyment, participants in a participatory or joint activity possess collective (or joint) rights.

Two common reasons explaining why moral group rights should be respected are described as group agency and group's well-being. According to philosophical literature, the degree of the agency required for grounding moral group rights resides in a group's decision making procedure (French, 1984; Preda, 2012). Aside from theories arguing for group agency as a reason for defending moral group rights, promoting group's well-being by realizing (non-)aggregative collective interests of group members is another popular reason. Following that, the moral group's right promotes group's well-being by realising aggregate or shared moral interests (Raz 1988) among group members, or by respecting diverse and non-aggregative moral interests (Finnis, 1998; Newman, 2004) among members.

According to the preceding discussion, to address moral group rights, a case-by-case investigation is required to determine whether the targeted group has an identity to be able to have rights as such, or whether members of a group can engage in a joint action

to hold rights jointly. On the other hand, we can consider if the group has agency, in which case assigning moral group rights to it is acceptable, or whether there are (non-)aggregative collective interests that, when realized, lead to the group's flourishing. As a result, defending moral group rights is feasible, but it depends on the nature of the group under consideration and how it is justified.

6. Concluding remarks: distinguish between concepts to adequately protect data subjects

The emergence of new decentralized data governance schemes motivated our exploration with citizens around how they perceive these novel tools. The results, while limited, would show that people would be interested in retaining agency over their personal data and, in some cases, they would be interested in engaging on a group-based approach to secure their rights, for example in the case of parents towards their children's data. On the other hand, individuals would not be interested in abandoning their rights and moving towards a common structure with other individuals. Current and proposed regulatory schemes would follow this trend by insisting on an individual-based approach.

In this sense, adopting a data commons approach would not be aligned with current social needs as well as it would demand a considerable rework of existing regulations; particularly on this, given the novelty of certain regulations, such as the Data Governance Act, it would seem that lawmakers have not supported such an approach, even if it was recently possible to change courses in regulation. Nevertheless, groups can play a role in ensuring better protection for data subjects, as analyzed in our section. To ensure such adequate protection, a clear distinction between the involved categories is necessary, particularly to identify who is involved with who, in order to allow trust to foster between the involved parties to a data processing activity.

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